

“Built by CDH” Software Warranty and *“Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement* document Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) commitment to and responsibilities for maintaining and supporting applications developed by the CDH Development & Design Team. These documents also spell out corresponding Project Director (PI) responsibilities toward the same goal, as well as the conditions under which a project will no longer be maintained by CDH, including the possibility that a site may eventually be archived and turned off, should it become unmaintainable or a security risk.

Maintenance plans are based on infrastructure provided by Princeton University Office of Information Technology (OIT), which provides Virtual Server hosting to faculty and departments with no cost or annual fee.

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“Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement

Summary

This document outlines the CDH’s on-going responsibilities to our projects and collaborators following the initial three-month warranty period. It covers how the CDH handles regular maintenance, including software updates and security patches, as well as a decision tree for handling major issues such as loss of core site functionality. New features, redesigns, or minor fixes are not covered.

In order for the Long Term Service Agreement (LTSA) to remain in effect, the project must be hosted on Princeton infrastructure and have a PI or designated faculty project contact currently employed by Princeton University. The CDH will involve Project PIs in the long term maintenance of their projects, including major updates and testing following software updates, restores, or major fixes. If the project cannot be fixed in a reasonable timeframe, it will be archived and all URLs will redirect to the CDH project page until it can be restored.

Any questions about the LTSA should be directed to CDH’s Lead Developer.

Projects Covered by LTSA

The CDH Long Term Service Agreement (LTSA) applies to projects built by the CDH Development and Design Team under a project charter and housed on Princeton OIT servers. Projects that result from Seed Grants, Dataset Curation Grant, graduate or postgraduate fellowships (including cohort work), unchartered staff projects, or projects CDH staff have consulted on but did not build, do not fall under this LTSA.

“Built by CDH” projects that have moved to external hosting can schedule consultations for advice on fixing major project issues or migrating to a new server environment, but CDH staff will not fix or migrate projects that are not hosted by Princeton after the warranty period ends.

Regular Maintenance

CDH Responsibilities

- Automated monitoring of website and codebase
- Add PI to Research Computing listserv announcing major infrastructure updates. CDH will be in touch with PI’s when testing following updates is required
- Database backups, following OIT standard procedure
- Relevant security updates to Django (or relevant platform) Long Term Service Release.
 - Six months before current LTS is deprecated, CDH will hold a meeting with PI or authorized Princeton contact to determine next steps (upgrade to next LTS and test, archive the project)

New features, redesigns, or bug fixes (major or minor) are not covered. New features or interface redesigns require a new agreement with the CDH - either a Project Enhancement Grant or a new Research Partnership, depending on the amount of work involved. Minor fixes may be worked into the development schedule at the discretion of the Lead Developer as CDH priorities permit.

Princeton-employed PI Responsibilities

The PI is responsible for testing the application following updates to either the codebase (CDH) or the underlying operating system (OIT). All requests for testing will include deadlines based on security concerns. If the PI does not respond by deadlines, maintenance will be paused. If this would cause a security threat on Princeton servers, then the application may be temporarily disabled and project URLs redirected to project page on CDH website. If the PI does not respond after the third communication attempt, and the site poses a security threat, it will be removed from our infrastructure and archived by the CDH. If the application does not pose a security threat it will remain up until such time as it loses core functionality or does pose a security threat. Then the VM will be archived.

The PI is responsible for reporting any loss of data or functionality, either to database or uploaded file content, as soon as possible so that CDH can work with OIT to restore from backups. Data losses reported after more than 10 days cannot be guaranteed to be restored.

PI Leaves Princeton

Faculty PIs with CDH chartered projects hosted on Princeton servers who leave Princeton have a 6 month grace period to find a new hosting solution for their project. By the end of the grace period, CDH will provide all necessary project materials and existing documentation to the new hosting institution.

If the PI chooses to host their project independently, CDH will provide all necessary project materials and documentation to redeploy the project. The PI can request consultations with CDH staff for advice, but CDH staff will not fix or migrate projects that are not hosted on Princeton infrastructure.

When a chartered project moves off Princeton servers, the migrated application and relevant source code must continue to credit the CDH with the original development of the project.

If the PI wants to keep hosting the project at Princeton they must designate a current Princeton faculty member as the new project contact, and an updated LTSA must be signed with that contact and the Lead Developer. If the PI retires, and receives emeritus status, then they must designate a co-contact person from the current Princeton faculty, modify the project's LTSA, and re-sign with the Lead Developer.

If the PI leaves Princeton without designating a new contact person or finding a new hosting solution for the project, CDH will archive a snapshot of the project and offer a copy of the snapshot to the PI. As long as the project works normally it will run on Princeton servers unless otherwise requested, but when it breaks or becomes a security risk, the application will be

turned off and the project URLs will redirect to the project's page on the CDH website. CDH will make a best faith effort to notify the PI when the project is taken offline.

Any extensions to this deadline must be approved by the Lead Developer no later than one month prior to the end of the grace period.

Major loss of functionality or critical security concerns

When a site has lost core functionality, if it is down and cannot be recovered from backup, or if there are critical security issues that require updating or restricting the server, the CDH Development and Design Team will spend up to 16 person hours fixing the site, in collaboration with the PI.

If the site cannot be fixed within 16 person hours, the Lead Developer will spend up to 4 person hours drafting a Statement of Work (SOW) for fixing the problem. In drafting the SOW, the Lead Developer determines the criteria for the fixed project to continue to be covered by this LTSA.

The Lead Developer and the PI will choose one of the following:

1. The PI can assemble resources necessary to complete SOW, either with CDH staff if available, other assistance on campus, or by hiring an external contractor.
 - a. If the work is extensive, the project URLs may be temporarily redirected to the project page on the CDH website, with updated text giving a timeline for the application relaunch
 - b. If the work is done by an outside contractor, it must be to specifications (i.e., documentation, technical stack, and open source code) that the CDH can maintain going forward, or the LTSA is void.
 - c. If the site moves off Princeton servers, the LTSA is void.
2. If the PI cannot assemble resources necessary to complete SOW, the CDH will provide the PI with a package of all unique files, folders, and data from the production server to be used for redeployment when resources are available. The CDH will also archive a copy of the packaged files. The hosting infrastructure will be turned off at OIT and all URLs redirected to the project page on the CDH website.

If the site must be shut down (either due to a critical security vulnerability that cannot be addressed or major loss of functionality and insufficient resources to complete an SOW) but is still functional enough to archive, the CDH will request that the University Archives archive it for preservation. A link to the archived website will be added to the CDH project page.

If the PI cannot be contacted within 2 weeks, CDH will archive a copy of production data before the broken project VM is turned off at OIT. All URLs will redirect to the project page on the CDH main website.